

Taxonomic Study on Family Araceae in Southern part of Kalama Taung Reserved Forest, Paung Township, Mon State

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Abstract

The present study deals with a taxonomic study on family Araceae in Southern part of Kalama Taung Reserved Forest, Paung Township, Mon State. This study feature was represented by 9 species belong to 9 genera of family Araceae. A total of 6 herbs and 3 climbers were recorded. An artificial key to the studied species were also constructed. Morphological characters, common names, flowering and fruiting period and Global Positioning System (GPS) are provided.

Key words: Araceae, Southern part of Kalama Taung Reserved Forest, artificial key

Introduction

Myanmar occupies an area of 678,033 sq km in Southeast Asia. Mon State extends 12,155 sq km at the southeast of Myanmar. Southern part of Kalama Taung Reserved Forest covers 39.292 square miles in Paung Township, Mon State. It is situated between North-latitude 16° 36' and 16° 50' and East-longitude 97° 25' and 97° 33'.

The family Araceae consists of about 110 genera and 1800 species, the vast majority of them tropical or subtropical (Cronquist, 1981). According to Kress *et al.* (2003), 35 genera and 106 species were recorded in checklist of Myanmar. The family Araceae distributed in cosmopolitan, with most species in tropical Southeast Asia, Africa, and America, fewer in temperate zones (Heywood *et al.*, 2007).

Perennial, mainly terrestrial, herbs with a variety of lifeforms, including geophytes, epiphytes, and climbers, rarely free-floating aquatics. The roots adventitious, often thickened, rhizomes or subglobose tubers. Leaves usually differentiated in petiole sheath, petiole, and an expanded leaf blade of variable shape. Inflorescence usually a dense spadix with numerous, ebracteate flowers and subtended by a conspicuous spathe. Flowers sessile and bi- or unisexual. Tepals often more or less connate in bisexual flowers and absent in the unisexual flowers. Ovary superior or embedded in the spadix and composed of 1 to 3, rarely more, with 1 to numerous ovules on basal, apical, axile, or parietal placentas; styles usually inconspicuous with lobed stigma. Fruit a berry, sometimes a utricle, a drupe, or nutlike, with 1 to many seeds (Heywood *et al.*, 2007).

The objective of this paper are to identify and to know the outstanding characters collected species in the study area.

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Fig. 1. Study Map of Southern part of Kalama Taung Reserved Forest

Materials and Methods

The specimens were collected from Southern part of Kalama Taung, Paung Township, Mon State during 2013-2016. The morphological characters of vegetative and reproductive parts and Global Positioning System (GPS) were recorded. The specimens were prepared and preserved based on the herbarium techniques of Lawrence (1964). The herbarium specimens were deposited in Herbarium of Yangon University for references and other researchers. The collected plant specimens were identified based on Backer and Bakhuizen (1968), Hooker (1894) and Peter *et al.* (2012)

Results

Nine species belong to nine genera of family Araceae were collected, identified, and classified according to APG III (2011) classification system.

Class – Equisetopsida			
Subclass - Magnoliidae			
Monocots			
Superorder	Order	Family	Scientific Name
Lilianaes	Alismatales	Araceae	(1) <i>Aglaonema nitidum</i> (Jack) Kunth
			(2) <i>Arisaema album</i> N.E. Br.
			(3) <i>Colocasia esculenta</i> (L.) Schott
			(4) <i>Homalomena rubescens</i> Kunth
			(5) <i>Lasia spinosa</i> (L.) Thw.
			(6) <i>Pothos scandens</i> L.
			(7) <i>Rhaphidophora pertusa</i> (Roxb.) Schott
			(8) <i>Scindapsus officinalis</i> (Roxb.) Schott
			(9) <i>Typhonium trilobatum</i> (L.) Schott

Key to the studied species:

1. Flowers unisexual ----- 5
 1. Flowers bisexual ----- 2
 2. Flower with perianth ----- 3
 2. Flower without perianth ----- 4
 3. Plants climbing; petioles winged ----- **6. *Pothos scandens***
 3. Plants erect ; petioles wingless ----- **5. *Lasia spinosa***
 4. Leaves margin deeply pinnatifid ----- **7. *Rhaphidophora pertusa***
 4. Leaves margin entire ----- **8. *Scindapsus officinalis***
 5. Suffruticose herbs ----- **1. *Aglaonema nitidum***
 5. Herbaceous plants of various life forms ----- 6
 6. Stamens entirely connate into a distinct synandrium -----
 ----- **3. *Colocasia esculenta***
 6. Stamens free or only filament connate (not synandrium) ----- 7
 7. Spadix appendix absent ----- **4. *Homalomena rubescens***
 7. Spadix appendix present ----- 8
 8. Leaf several together, simple, deeply 3-lobed ----- **9. *Typhonium trilobatum***
 8. Leaf solitary, trifoliate ----- **2. *Arisaema album***

1. *Aglaonema nitidum* (Jack) Kunth, Enum. Pl. 3: 56. 1841.

Calla nitida Jack, Enum. Pl. 3:56.1841.

Evergreen herb; stem erect, about 40 cm high; internodes short. Leaves forming an apical crown, simple; petioles sheathing at base; leaf blade lanceolate, 10-20 x 4-7 cm, base

rounded, apex acuminate. Peduncle erect, 4-8 cm long, deflexed in fruiting; spathe and spadix persistent. Spathe ovate, 5-7 cm long, decurrent, apex apiculate, green to yellowish white. Spadix 3-5 cm long, cylindrical, stipitate. Flowers unisexual. Male flowers free; filaments distinct connective thickened. Female flowers: ovary globose, one ovule in a single locule, basal placentation; style short and thick; stigma disciform, central concave. Fruit an ellipsoid berry; seed solitary, ellipsoid.

Common name: Kyauk-sein-gamon

Flowering and Fruiting period: April to July

Specimen examined: Oak-ta-tar Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 39' 45.0", E- 097° 27' 40.3", Altitude- 165 m; 28-May-2015; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 323 (RGN-20018).

2. *Arisaema album* N.E. Br., Journ. Linn. Soc.Bot. 18. 247.1882.

Herbs to 70 cm high; tuber depressed globose, 2-5 cm in wide. Leaves solitary, trifoliolate; petioles 25-45 long; petiolules about 1 cm long; leaflets blade elliptic-ovate, 12-23 x 6-12 cm, base attenuate, apex acuminate, lateral leaflets slightly asymmetrical. Peduncle slightly shorter than petiole. Spathe tube cylindrical, 4.0-4.5 x 2.0-2.5 cm, widening at the top, with a distinct and expanded; spathe mouth 9-12 x 6-7 cm, apex acuminate and widely recurved. Spadix slightly exserted, appendage filiform, bearing scattered subulate neuters. Female zone subcylindric, 2.5-4.0 x 0.8-1.3 cm, sessile. Female flowers densely packed; ovaries ovoid, 4-6 ovules in locule; stigma on a short style, penicillate, 1.0-1.5 mm long.

Common name: Wa-u

Flowering and Fruiting period: May to August

Specimen examined: Kalama Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 41' 19.7", E- 097° 27' 36.4", Altitude- 890 m; 20-May-2013; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 007 (RGN-20019)

3. *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott, Melet. Bot. 18. 1832.

Arum esculentum L., Sp. Pl. 2:965.1753.

Underground stem 10-15 cm high; rhizome horizontal. Leaves spirally arranged, simple; petioles with sheath-like dilated towards base; leaf blades peltate, ovate-triangular, 20-50 x 15-25 cm, base cordate with bilobed, margin slightly undulate. Peduncles solitary, 15-25 cm long. Spathe tube oblong, 2.5-3.0 x 1.0-2.0 cm, constricted, enveloping pistillate region, afterwards navicular shape, margin convolute; limb elliptic, 6-11 x 3-4 cm. Spadix 6-10 cm long, in 4 parts: lower pistillate region conic, 3.0-3.5 x 0.8-1.2 cm, ovary spirally arranged, ovoid, 2.5-3.0 mm long, unilocular with many ovules, parietal placentation, stigma depressed-globose; intermediate sterile narrowly cylindrical; middle staminate region cylindrical, stamens 3-6 united, synandria with marginal thecae; appendix region narrowly conic, 4.0-4.5 x 0.5-0.8 cm.

Common name: Pein

Flowering and Fruiting period: June to September

Specimen examined: Mu-kyi Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 35' 51.0", E- 097° 29' 09.0", Altitude- 25 m; 7-July-2014; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 114 (RGN-20020).

4. *Homalomena rubescens* (Roxb.) Kunth, Enum. Pl. 3. 57. 1841.

Calla rubescens Roxb., Fl. Ind. 3. 515. 1832.

Robust herb, 30-70 cm high; stem erect and later decumbent, smelling of camphor. Leaves several together; petioles 15-35 cm long, tinged red; petiolar sheath 4-10 cm long, margins membranous; leaf blade ovate-sagittate, 20-30 x 10-17 cm, base cordate-sagittate. Peduncle 10-20 cm long, erect to declinate; spathe oblong, 7-10 cm long; spadix tapering cylindrical, 7-9 cm long, slightly equaling spathe, stipes about 5 mm long. Pistillate flower region 1.5-2.5 x 0.5-1.0 cm; ovary ovoid-globose, about 2 mm in diameter; stigma sessile, capitate; staminode clavate, ivory-colored. Staminate flower region 5.5-6.0 cm long; stamens rhombo-hexagonal in plane view, 2-3 mm in diameter.

Common name: Sit-ton-ni; Oo-mon-kya

Flowering and Fruiting period: May to August

Specimen examined: Mu-kyi Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 36' 21.0", E- 097° 29' 17.6", Altitude- 255 m; 14-May-2016; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 391 (RGN-20021).

5. *Lasia spinosa* (L.) Thw., Enum. Pl. Zeyl. 336. 1864.

Dracontium spinosum L., Sp. Pl. 2: 967. 1753.

Erect herbs, 1-2 m tall; stem prostrate, about 4 cm thick. Petioles 10-30 cm long, laxly prickly; leaf blade sagittate-hastate, 20-50 x 15-40 cm, margin deeply pinnatifid, midrib of lower surface curved prickles. Peduncles 20-45 cm long, laxly prickly. Spathe open 6-10 cm long and 4 cm wide at lower to expose spadix, caudate part 18-35 cm long, twisted. Spadix cylindrical, 3.0-5.0 x 0.7-1.0 cm. Flowers spiral, bisexual. Tepals 4-6, vaulted truncate, apex triangular hooded and keeled. Stamens 4-6; filaments 1.0-1.5 long; anther elliptic, about 0.7 mm. Ovary ovoid, unilocule with a single ovule; stigma orbicular.

Common name: Za-yit

Flowering and Fruiting period: September to December

Specimen examined: Nwar -la-bok Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 38' 57.3", E- 097° 29' 27.3", Altitude- 488 m ; 17-November-2014; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 204 (RGN-20022).

6. *Pothos scandens* L., Sp. Pl. 968. 1753.

Lianas, to 9 m high; stems subterete. Leaves distichous, simple; petiole 1.5-4.0 x 0.6-1.0 cm, broadly winged, base decurrent, apex emarginate; leaf blade elliptic, 3.0-12.0 x 3.0-5.0 cm, base rounded, apex acuminate. Flowering shoot arising from distal leaf axils. Peduncle 1-2 cm long, green, entirely enveloped by sheath like prophyll, 3-10 mm long; spathe greenish, ovate, concave, 4-8 x 4-7 mm, margins rolled, apex rounded to acute with a tiny mucro. Spadix globose, 0.5-1.0 cm; stipes terete, 0.5-1.0 cm long. Tepals 6, apex vaulted-truncate. Stamens 6, equal; filaments strap shaped; anther ovoid. Carpels trilocular; stigma sessile, umbilicate. Berry ellipsoid, 1.0-1.5 x 0.8-1.2 cm, green to red.

Common name: Thit-kat-pin

Flowering and Fruiting period: October to March

Specimen examined: Win-ga-bar Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 40' 36.1", E- 097° 28' 07.6", Altitude- 738 m; 29-December-2013; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 055 (RGN-20023).

7. *Rhaphidophora pertusa* (Roxb.) Schott, Prodr. Syst. Aroid. 382. 1860.

Pothos pertusus Roxb., Fl. Ind. 1: 455. 1820.

Robust climbing herb, about 9 m high. Leaves alternate; petiole 20-55 cm long, deeply channelled; leaf blade broadly ovate, 20-50 x 15-35 cm, base subcordate, margin pinnatisect, apex cuspidate, with large whole. Peduncles 5.0-18.0 cm long. Spathe oblong, 7-10 x 3-6 cm, apex acuminate, coriaceous, soon withering and deciduous. Spadix cylindrical, 8.0-15.0 x 1.5-2.5 cm. Stamens 4; filaments flattened, 2-3 x 1-1.5 mm; anthers ellipsoid, ditheous, basifixed. Ovary 2-loculed, 4-angled, many ovules; style conic; stigma punctuate, immersed in truncate style.

Common name: Not known

Flowering and Fruiting period: July to October

Specimen examined: Mu-kyi Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 35' 50.1", E- 097° 29' 05.6", Altitude- 26 m; 30-September-2014; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 161 (RGN-20024).

8. *Scindapsus officinalis* (Roxb.) Schott, Melet. Bot.: 21. 1832.

Pothos officinalis Roxb., Fl. Ind. 1: 452. 1820.

Lianas, up to 20 m high. Leaves spiro-distichous, simple; petiole 7-15 cm long; petiolar sheath spreading winged along petiole length; leaf blade ovate-elliptic, 8-20 x 6-10 cm long, base rounded, slightly oblique. Peduncle cylindrical, 3-10 x 1.0-1.5 cm long, subtended by a foliage leaf. Spathe broadly cigar-shaped, 11-16 x 3-5 cm long, long-beaked. Spadix cylindrical, 6.0-11.0 x 1.0-2.5 cm, sessile. Stamens 4; filaments flattened; anthers oblong-ellipsoid. Ovary compressed rhomboid, 4-6 angular; styles truncate; stigma punctuate. Infructescence fusiform, 10-15 x 2-4 cm.

Common name: Sin-peik-chin

Flowering and Fruiting period: May to September

Specimen examined: Ko-gwe, Paung Township; N- 16° 42' 09.3", E- 097° 30' 02.9", Altitude- 53 m; 15-May-2016; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 397 (RGN-20025).

9. *Typhonium trilobatum* (L.) Schott, Wiener Z. Kunst 3: 72. 1829.

Arum trilobatum L., Sp. Pl. 2: 965. 1753.

Stem 15-40 cm high; tuberous rhizome subglobose. Leaves several together, simple; petiole 12-30 cm long; leaf blade cordate-ovate, deeply 3-lobed, 10-15 x 6-11 cm, central lobe ovate. Spathe convolute at base, ovoid, 2.0-4.0 x 2.0-2.5 cm, constricted at the top; limb ovate-lanceolate, 10-20 x 5-9 cm, spreading, inside reddish purple. Spadix shorter than spathe; female zone conic, 7-10 mm, ovary yellowish green, stigma disciform; sterile zone 2-3 cm long, staminodes vermiform, numerous, strongly curled and twisted; male zone 1.5-2.0 x 0.4-0.7 cm, stamens pink; appendix narrowly elongate conical, 5.0-10.0 x 0.4-0.6 cm, base truncate, with 2 mm stipe at the base, apex acuminate, reddish.

Common name: Not known

Flowering and Fruiting period: May to August

Specimen examined: Ka-ton village, Zingyaik Taung, Paung Township; N- 16° 42' 23.5", E- 097° 25' 29.4", Altitude- 25 m; 16-May-2016; Thant Zaw Win, Coll. no. 400 (RGN- 20026).

A. *Aglaonema nitidum*
(Jack) Kunth

B. *Arisaema album* N. E. Br.

C. *Colocasia esculenta* (L.)
Schott

D. *Homalomena rubescens*
Kunth

E. *Lasia spinosa* (L.) Thw.

F. *Pothos scandens* L.

G. *Rhapsidophora pertusa*
(Roxb.) Schott

H. *Scindapsus officinalis*
(Roxb.) Schott

I. *Typhonium trilobatum*
(L.) Schott

Discussion and Conclusion

The present paper deals with Araceae family in Southern part of Kalama Taung Reserved Forest, Paung Township, Mon State. The collected 9 genera and 9 species in Araceae family belong to order Alismatales, superorder Lilianae under subclass Magnoliidae.

A total of 6 terrestrial herbs and 3 climbers herbs were recorded. *Aglaonema nitidum*, *Arisaema album*, *Colocasia esculenta*, *Homalomena rubescens*, *Lasia spinosa* and *Typhonium trilobatum* are terrestrial herbs. *Pothos scandens*, *Rhaphidophora pertusa* and *Scindapsus officinalis* are climbing herbs.

Aglaonema nitidum, *Colocasia esculenta*, *Homalomena rubescens* and *Scindapsus officinalis* are simple leaves. The leaf of *Arisaema album* is trifoliolate, and *Typhonium trilobatum* is deeply 3-lobed.

This present paper is dedicated to known outstanding characters of collected plant species of family Araceae, and partially help for the compilation of Flora of Myanmar.

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